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Evaluation of cassava yield response to iron rates grown in a tropical rain forest soils of South-eastern Nigeria

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A two year field experiments were conducted to determine the effect of Fe application rates on cassava performance grown in an acidic sandy soil in Nigeria. The results showed that application of iron sulphate significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased plant height, Fe concentration, Fe uptake and tuber yields of cassava. Cassava tuber yield response to iron sulphate fertilization followed a

second-order equation, with the maximum production at Fe rate of $16.0 \text{ kg Fe ha}^{-1}$. In conclusion, application of FeSO_4 at a rate of $16.0 \text{ kg Fe ha}^{-1}$ was recommended for cassava production in a tropical rain forest soil of South-eastern Nigeria.

Keywords: DMY, EDTA, Fe uptake, FeSO_4 , maximum tuber yield

INTRODUCTION

Micronutrients such as Fe, Cu, Mn and Zn are required in small amount by plants and these are known to enhance the actions of some enzymes which aid in the growth and yield of major food crops (Fageria *et al.*, 2002). Due to more intensive crop production with higher yields and heavier application of N, P and K fertilizers increases the need for Fe and in fact other micronutrients (Cu, Mn and Zn) in agriculture (Effiong and Ibia, 2009).

Root and tuber crops, including yam, cassava, potato and sweet potato are the most important food crops for direct human consumption in Africa. Cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) belongs to the family Euphorbiaceae (Nweke *et al.*, 2002) and is amongst the root and tuber crops, which are very important food crops for direct human and animal consumption in Africa (Howeler, 2002; Ezui *et al.*, 2015). The crop is grown in varied agro-ecological environments and production systems ranging from highland densely populated regions to lowland drier areas prone to droughts or floods (Ugwu *et al.*, 2019). Cassava has long been considered a commercialized crop for export (IITA, 2018, NRCRI, 2018). The leaves

are used as a leaf vegetable. Other important products produced from cassava are starch, beer, vinegar and alcohol (Odiyi and Bamidele, 2014).

According to FAOSTAT (2014), the world production of fresh cassava roots increased tremendously from 176 to 277 million Mt between 2000 and 2013. West Africa for instance, produces about 28% of the world's cassava and the rest of Africa 26% (FAOSTAT, 2014). The increase in cassava production was attained through both expansion of the cultivated area and increased yields of cassava (Ezui *et al.*, 2015). Although average yields in West Africa increased between 2000 and 2013 from 9.7 to 13 Mt ha^{-1} of fresh roots (FAOSTAT, 2014), a large yield gap remains, given that yields close to 60 Mt ha^{-1} have been attained in researcher-managed fields in the region (Odedina *et al.*, 2009). Recent research has proven that added micronutrients have a measurable impact on human micronutrient status (FAO, WFP and IFAD, 2012).

The fertilizer recommendations for cassava production found in most countries in West Africa are usually blanket recommendations, regardless of agro-ecological or soil

diversity (FAO, WFP and IFAD, 2012; Ezui *et al.*, 2015). This can contribute to increase nutrient losses (Cassman *et al.*, 2002) and, low productivity and profitability of cassava yields (Angus *et al.*, 2004). Appropriate sufficient supply of Fe fertilizer based on balanced nutrition may contribute to reducing cassava yield gaps thereby increase cassava root production (Howeler, 2002; Kabata-Pendias, 2011).

Available information on Fe status in soil and nutrition for cassava production in Nigeria and elsewhere is currently scarce. However, investigations carried out so far have revealed that there is Fe deficiency in coastal plain sandy soils of South Eastern Nigeria (Udoh *et al.*, 2008; Eteng *et al.*, 2014 and 2015; Essien and Eteng, 2016). The aim of this study were to: (i) determine the status of Fe in soils, and (ii) to evaluate the optimum levels of Fe for maximum growth and yield of cassava in a coastal plain sand soils of south eastern Nigeria

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of the study area

The field experimental area was located at National Root Crop Research Institute (NRCRI) Umudike, South-eastern Nigeria. NRCRI Umudike is located between latitude 05° 29¹ N and longitudes 07° 33¹ E and at an elevation of 122 m above sea level (NRCRI, 2017). The area is characterized with monthly mean minimum and maximum temperature range of 21-34°C, and the average rainfall of about 2200 mm per annum (NRCRI, 2017).

Experimental design and treatments

The field experiment was conducted between 2016 and 2018 cropping seasons to estimate the optimum iron level and maximum cassava uptake (kg ha⁻¹) in coastal plain sand soil. A cassava variety TMS 01/1368 (UMUCASS 38), a yellow tuber stem cuttings of approximately 4-5 cm in length and with 6-7 nodes were arranged according to a randomized complete block design (RCBD), with six experimental treatments replicated four times to give 24 experimental plots. Each experimental plot had five (5) ridges measuring 5.0 by 4.0 m (20 m²), with inter-block and inter-plot spacing of 1 and 0.5 m, respectively. A two m-wide pathway was maintained around the entire experimental area. The cassava cuttings were sown at the spacing of 1m x 1 m to give a plant population of 10,000 plants per hectare.

The six rates of Fe (0, 4, 8, 12, 16 and 20 kg ha⁻¹) FeSO₄.5H₂O in granulated form, were mixed with sharp sands and applied on the ridge crest as band placement, two weeks after sprouting. A recommended basal dosage of 120 kg N ha⁻¹ as urea; 60 kg P₂O₅ ha⁻¹ as single super

phosphate, SSP, and 60 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ as muriate of potash, MOP as basal N, P and K fertilizers, were respectively were also applied uniformly at two weeks after planting (WAP) as recommended for this region (Chude *et al.*, 2012). Weeding was done thrice throughout the cropping period to maintain a clean farm environment.

In the second year of cropping, the same field, according to the experimental design and field layers were maintained, respectively. No experimental treatments were applied unless the basal recommended N, P and K fertilizers to ensure that the fertility status of the soil was maintained.

Agronomy data collection

Several growth and yield components such as; plant height, stem girth, number of branches, leaf area and leaf area index were measured at 3, 6, and 9 months after planting. At the end of study, 9 months after planting, the final tuber/root yield was determined and recorded. Iron uptake (kg ha⁻¹) in cassava roots were calculated as the product of Fe concentration (mg kg⁻¹) and the dry matter yield (kg ha⁻¹) /100. The cassava dry matter yield, Fe concentration and Fe uptake values were used as yield parameters of the cassava plants.

Soil and plant sample analysis

Five core surface soil samples (0-20 cm) each from ten (10) cassava fields, located across Abia State, were collected bulked together and a composite soil sample was collected and air-dried, screened through a 2 mm sieve and analyzed using standard methods for some physical and chemical characteristics. The 2 mm sieved soils were analyzed for particle size analysis by the hydrometer method (Gee and Or, 2002); Soil pH (soil: water ratio of 1: 2.5) was determined with a combined electrode pH meter (Thomas, 1996); Soil organic carbon was determined by the potassium dichromate wet oxidation method (Nelson and Sommer, 1996). Exchangeable cations were extracted with neutral ammonium acetate and the Na and K contents were determined using flame photometer method whereas the Mg and Ca contents were determined by the EDTA complexometric titration method. Total exchangeable acidity (TEA) was determined using Mclean (1982) method. Total exchangeable bases (TEB) were obtained by summation of exchangeable cations (Ca, Mg, K and Na) values (Thomas, 1996) while, the effective cations exchange capacity (ECEC) was determined by the method described by Sumner and Miller (1996). For the determination of available Fe contents in soils, 0.05M EDTA extractant was used (Whitney, 1988). Soil samples were shaken with 0.05 M EDTA in a ratio of soil-solution (1:2) for 30 minutes (Eteng and Asawalam, 2015).

After shaking, the soil-solution was centrifuged and filtered through Whatman filter paper No. 42. The quantity of Fe content in the soil sample was performed with an atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS) (UNICAM model SOLAAR 32: Fe ASTM D1068).

To determine DMY and nutrient concentration, the cassava materials (tuber/roots) were harvested at three months (90 days) after planting, rinsed in distilled water, pre-dried under the sun to remove excess water and later packed in large brown envelopes and oven-dried at 120°C for 72 hours. After drying to constant weight, the dried materials were weighed and recorded as dry matter yield (DMY g plant⁻¹). The oven-dried and ground cassava materials were digested using sulphuric acid, nitric acid and perchloric acid (H₂SO₄:HNO₃:HClO₄) at a ratio of 1:2:3 method of Shuman (1991) in Teflon crucible, and heated on a hot plate. The digest was filtered and the filtrate or extract was analyzed for Fe contents (conc. mg kg⁻¹) in cassava plants using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS: Pre UNICAM model 939).

Statistical analysis

The data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) procedure, using general linear model of Genstat and PASW Statistics 18 for Window 7.0. Significant means were separated using Fisher's least significant difference (LSD) and appropriated at P<0.05 (two-tailed). Also Pearson correlation as well as regression analyses at different probability levels were conducted to evaluate optimum Fe levels and predict maximum uptake in cassava. The graphical analysis was performed using PASW Statistics software, version 18 for Window 7.0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of soil fertility

Some physical and chemical properties of the soil samples where the plants were grown are indicated in (Table 1). In the (Table 1), pH values of the soil samples ranged from 4.01 to 5.89 with an average of 4.84, suggesting that the soils are very strongly acidic. The total organic carbon content ranged from 8.32 to 15.63 gkg⁻¹, with an average of 12.31 g kg⁻¹. This suggests that, higher percent of the soils were low in organic carbon content (Tandon, 1995). The low organic carbon values may be as a result of high mineralization rate due to intensive farming (Aruleba and Ogunkunle, 2006). Intensive cultivation is known to favour a rapid mineralization of organic matter. This finding is in agreement with those of Udom *et al.* (2004), Ayuba *et al.* (2007), Ibia and Udo, (2009). The ECEC values varied

widely between 5.92 and 14.42 cmol kg⁻¹ with an average of 9.57 cmol kg⁻¹. However, ECEC of most of the soils tested were below 12 cmol kg⁻¹ and are rated low as established by Melsted *et al.* (1969) for fertile soils, and this is the range of critical value for soils that are dominated by oxide and hydroxide clays. However, Aluko *et al.* (2001) noted that ECEC values between 10 and 20 Cmol kg⁻¹ are considered marginally adequate for crop production. Based on this assessment, and in comparison with the values reported for Nigeria soils, the soils of the study area have moderate ECEC values that can sustain crop production for a short cropping season. The result further suggests that most of the soils may have few exchange sites. Most of the soils samples determined were coarse texture and the textural class was dominated by sandy clay loam (SCL). The results are at par with that of Akinrinde *et al.* (2005), Ayuba *et al.* (2007) and Ibrahim *et al.* (2011).

Total and extractable Fe in the soils is indicated in (Table 1). Total Fe in the soils varied widely and ranged from 27.23 to 47.63 mg kg⁻¹, with an average of 36.16 mg kg⁻¹. The contents of total Fe determined in the soils can be compared to values reported by Shittu *et al.* (2010), Ibrahim *et al.* (2011) and Sha'Ato *et al.* (2012) but are lower, when compared to values reported for other Nigerian soils (Amalu, 1991), probably due to the influence of the parent materials and low CEC of the soil (Kabata-Pendias, 2011; Sha'Ato *et al.*, 2012).

The content of extractable Fe in the soils varied widely depending on the location in which the soil samples were collected (Table 1). The EDTA-extractable Fe varied widely from 4.52 to 11.15 mg kg⁻¹ with an average value of 7.51 mg kg⁻¹. The EDTA-extractable Fe result obtained agreed with various studies reported by Eteng *et al.* (2015) and Essien and Eteng, (2016) who noted that there is deficiency of Fe in soils of coastal plain sand of south-eastern Nigeria. The soil used in this study could therefore be rated low to marginally sufficient in available Fe for cassava production which necessitate Fe nutrition for maximum yield of tropical tuber crops (Sha'Ato *et al.*, 2012). Nevertheless, Chude *et al.* (2012) noted that due to excessive rainfall, leaching and intensively cultivated soils of south-eastern Nigeria will sooner or later become deficient in available Fe. Marschner, (2012) earlier observed that any deficiency of available Fe in the soils may be due to the variability in the concentration due to the parent material which in this case, is a coastal plain sand soil (Ogban *et al.*, 1999; Kparamwang *et al.*, 2000).

Effect of Fe application rates on cassava performance

Cassava height

Data on plant height of the cassava plant for the first and second cropping are shown on (Table 2). The cassava heights decreased from the first year of cropping to the

Table 1. Sampling locations by state in the coastal plain sands soils of southeastern Nigeria.

Soil Sample Location	Chemical properties					Physical properties			Soil Texture
	pH (CaCl ₂)	TOC (gkg ⁻¹)	ECEC (cmolk ⁻¹)	Iron in soils (mgkg ⁻¹)		Particle size distribution (gkg ⁻¹)			
				Total Fe	Ext. Fe	Sand	Silt	Clay	
Mean	4.84	12.31	9.57	36.16	7.51	662.17	133.89	203.94	SCL
Min	4.01	8.32	5.92	27.23	4.52	491.54	28.20	82.18	
Max	5.89	15.63	17.42	47.63	11.15	864.61	165.18	362.25	

Table 2. Cassava height, cassava root dry matter and Fe concentration in cassava root grown on soils of southeastern Nigeria.

Fe rate (kg ha ⁻¹)	Cassava height (cm)		Cassava root dry matter (kg ha ⁻¹)		Fe concentration in cassava root (mg kg ⁻¹)	
	1 st cropping	2 nd cropping	1 st cropping	2 nd cropping	1 st cropping	2 nd cropping
0	105.83	65.68	13.45	10.07	35.80	21.27
4	117.90	74.75	19.75	13.19	46.50	38.45
8	123.98	79.30	25.83	19.91	71.10	53.38
12	139.15	89.45	28.37	22.93	83.50	75.09
16	149.73	92.70	36.84	30.89	115.57	98.30
20	141.38	86.87	26.26	22.84	84.33	70.56
Mean	129.66	81.46	25.08	19.97	72.86	59.51
LSD (0.05)	10.89	5.83	8.74	7.69	31.42	21.27
CV (%)	70.68	70.85	23.39	20.82	79.77	71.07

second year of cropping due to nutrient uptake the first season cassava cultivation. However, the application of 16.0 kg ha⁻¹ dosage of FeSO₄.5H₂O fertilizer produced higher plant heights of 149.73 and 92.70 cm while, the control yielded lower plant height (105.83 and 65.68 cm) with means of 129.66 and 81.46 cm for first and second seasons of cropping, respectively.

Cassava root dry matter

Data on dry matter yield of the cassava roots harvested at 3 months after planting during the first and second cropping are shown on (Table 2). The cassava dry matter yield determined, also decreased from the first year of cropping to the second year of cropping. The fertilization of Fe at 16.0 kg ha⁻¹ produced significantly (P<0.05) higher dry matter yield of 36.84 and 30.89 kg ha⁻¹ of cassava roots while, the control yielded lower dry matter of 13.45 and 10.07 kg ha⁻¹ with means of 25.08 and 19.97 kg ha⁻¹ of cassava roots, for first and second seasons of cropping, respectively.

Generally, dry matter yield cassava increased from control to 16.0 kg Fe ha⁻¹ levels of application and thereafter declined in yield to 20 kg Fe ha⁻¹ levels, respectively suggesting that Fe is one of the limiting essential mineral nutrients. This result suggests that the 16 kg Fe ha⁻¹ levels of application could be the optimum level of Fe in these soils for cassava. Similar results were reports by Adiloglu, (2003); Tening and Omuiti, (2011) for other crops.

Fe concentration in cassava root

Data on Fe concentration in cassava roots for the first and second cropping are shown on (Table 2). The Fe concentration obtained was higher in the first year of cropping than those obtained from the second year probably, due to nutrient mining from the first season cassava cultivation. However, the application of 16.0 mgkg⁻¹ dosage of FeSO₄.5H₂O fertilizer produced significantly (P<0.05) higher Fe concentrations of 115.57 and 98.30 mgkg⁻¹ in cassava roots while, the control yielded lower Fe concentration of 35.80 and 21.27 mgkg⁻¹ with means of 72.86 and 59.51 mgkg⁻¹ for first and second seasons of cropping, respectively. The wide variability as observed in this study may be as a result of deficiency of available Fe content in the soils under reviewed. The effect of Fe application on the yield parameter of cassava plants was determined to be significant at 5% level and the results obtained in this study are in agreement with those reported by Adiloglu (2003; Tening and Omueti, (2011) for other crops grown elsewhere in some Nigeria soils.

Prediction of optimum Fe rates for cassava production in soils of south-eastern Nigeria

Effects of Fe application on Fe uptake of cassava is presented in (Figure 1). The Fe uptake of the cassava roots obtained from the first and second cropping

Figure 1. Prediction of optimum Fe rates for cassava production in coastal plain sand soil.

Table 3. Maximum uptake, optimum Fe rate and coefficient of determination of cassava root

Cropping season	Tuber yield prediction (Regression equation)	Maximum Fe uptake (Y) (t ha ⁻¹)	Optimum Fe rate (X) (kg ha ⁻¹)	Coefficient of determination (R ²)
First	$Y = 3.9287 + 2.1737x - 0.0697x^2$	20.94	16.09	0.91
Second	$Y = 1.7299 + 1.7299x - 0.0546x^2$	14.92	15.84	0.82

determined at 3 months after planting increased with increasing Fe application (Figure 1). In the first and second cropping seasons, the application of 16.0 and 15.0 kg Fe ha⁻¹ produced significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher Fe uptake of 22.79 and 17.09 kg ha⁻¹ while, lower Fe uptake of 5.58 and 3.27 kg ha⁻¹ were determined from the control with relative uptake means of 15.45 and 10.51 kg ha⁻¹, respectively. From the polynomial regression equation (Figure 1), the maximum uptake, optimum Fe rate and coefficient of determination of cassava root are presented. The Table and the Figure have it that the application of 16.09 and 15.84 kg Fe ha⁻¹ produced 20.94 and 14.92 t ha⁻¹ of Fe uptake in cassava roots harvested at 3 MAP for the first and second cropping, respectively whereas, the predicted regression polynomial equation confirmed the levels of Fe nutrition on the field tuber yield result as presented in (Table 4). Their respective coefficient of determinant (r^2) is also presented in (Figure 1 and Table 3). Generally, the wide variability observed for Fe uptake in cassava roots harvested at 3 months after planting may be due to heavy rainfall which results to leaching and nutrient mining of available Fe content in the soils of southeastern Nigeria (Ibia and Udo 2009).

Effect of Fe nutrition on cassava tuber/root yields

Data on cassava roots yield produced from the first and second cropping seasons are presented in (Table 4). The cassava roots yield was higher in the first year of cropping than those obtained from the second year probably, due to nutrient mining from the first season cassava cultivation. However, the application of 16.0 kg ha⁻¹ dosage of FeSO₄.5H₂O fertilizer produced significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher cassava roots yield of 27.70 and 24.78 t ha⁻¹ while, the control yielded lower cassava roots yield of 12.17 and 9.65 t ha⁻¹ with means of 21.97 and 18.74 t ha⁻¹ for first and second seasons of cropping, respectively. It was evident from (Table 4) that all the Fe treated plots significantly ($P < 0.05$) increased the tuber yields over the control, as there was a consistent increase in tuber yield up to 16 kg Fe ha⁻¹, however, further addition to 20.0 kg Fe ha⁻¹ did not significantly result in corresponding yield increase (Table 4). The results however, shows that in both the first and second planting seasons, highest cassava tuber yields (27.70 and 24.78 t ha⁻¹) were produced with 16.0 kg Fe ha⁻¹ application rate followed by 12 and 20.0 kg Fe ha⁻¹

Table 4. Effect of Fe treatment rates on cassava tuber yield cassava tuber yield.

Fe Treatment levels (kg ha ⁻¹)	Tuber/root yields (tha ⁻¹)		Mean yield (tha ⁻¹)
	First Planting season	Second Planting season	
0	12.17	9.65	10.91
4	19.07	15.70	17.39
8	22.83	19.80	21.32
12	24.15	20.46	22.31
16	27.70	24.78	26.24
20	25.87	22.06	23.97
Mean	21.97	18.74	20.35
LSD (P<0.05)	3.55	4.32	
CV (%)	43.94	38.49	

application rates which did not differ significantly showing that both treatments are adequate for cassava tuber yield improvement.

Moreover, considering the low levels of available Fe in the soil (Table 1), Fe uptake cassava roots (Figure 1) and the maximum tuber yield obtained at 16 kg Fe ha⁻¹ (Table 4) it is evidence that FeSO₄.5H₂O application at this level is appropriate for cassava production in the soils. However, the application of Fe fertilizers to the cassava crop in different cropping seasons, not only enhances its production in the soils, but also increases tissue content and this can cure the micronutrients deficiency problem in human nutrition (Rengel *et al.*, 1999; Welch, 2002; White and Brown, 2010). The study further suggests that Fe was a limiting essential nutrient element for root and tuber crop production.

Conclusion and recommendation

The study demonstrated that, the application of Fe fertilizer at a rate of 16.0 kg ha⁻¹ improved all of cassava plant traits, it was concluded that the studied area suffers from Iron deficiency. So, application of Fe fertilizer is recommended for cassava root improvement by 56 percent. In this study, soil test and field experiments were conducted to estimate nutrient levels in the soil and together with plant analysis and crop yield are important agronomic tools for determining crop nutrient needs, predicting the nutrient-deficient areas and preventing the deficiency. Different soils of coastal plain sand significantly influenced total and available Fe. The use of Fe fertilizer improved cassava tuber yields appreciably while, different rates of Fe fertilization significantly influenced plant height, dry matter yield, and nutrient uptake and cassava root yield respectively. The application of 16.0 kg ha⁻¹ dosage of FeSO₄.5H₂O fertilizer produced significantly (P<0.05) higher plant height, dry matter yield, Fe concentration, respectively. Also, the application of 16.0 kg Fe ha⁻¹ produced significantly (P<0.05) higher Fe uptake of 22.79 and 17.09 kg ha⁻¹ in cassava roots harvested at 3 months for the first and second cropping seasons over the control.

Similarly 16.0 kg ha⁻¹ dosage of FeSO₄.5H₂O fertilizer produced significantly (P<0.05) higher cassava roots yield of 27.70 and 24.78 t ha⁻¹ in the first and second cropping seasons over the control. The rate of 16 kg Fe ha⁻¹ is recommended for maximum cassava tuber yields and to ensure that the yield potential is reached after optimization of Zn application.

Authors' declaration

We declared that this study is an original research by our research team and we agree to publish it in the journal.

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